

ISic0646

I.Sicily inscription 0646

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cupa

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mutyca

Place of origin (modern)

Modica

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Rome, private collection

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332959

1. Ούεττηίου τὸ σᾶμα τοῦ Βοός, ξένε,
2. τόδ' ἴσθι· νούσωι δ' ἀργαλῆι τακέντα νιν
3. ἔθαψε μάτηρ· ἄκριτος δο [κεῖ] Τύχα·
4. ὁ πέτρο ς ἔστι μάρτυς, ῶι κάλ [υ] πτε γᾶ.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644888

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Bibliography

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Manganaro, G. 2012. Un piccolo monumento funerario del tipo "cupa" da Modica con l'epigramma in greco di Vettios figlio di Bous e las peste "antonina". *Epigraphica.* 74: 441-445.

Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité.* 106: 79-118. At 107-108 no.20 fig.27-29

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